

Journal of Political Science (JPS)

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Scope & Topics

Journal of Political Science (JPS) is an open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles on both domestic and international politics. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on national and international politics. All submissions must describe original research, not published or currently under review for another conference or journal.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Comparative Politics
- Foreign Policy
- Institutionalism
- International Relations
- National & International Politics
- Politics & Society
- Public Law
- Public Policy

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through [Submission System](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : November 15, 2024**
- Notification : December 16, 2024
- Final Manuscript Due : December 23, 2024
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : jpsjournal@airccse.com or jps@aircconline.com

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